

The role of "green shipping" in reducing the greenhouse effect. Alternative fuels. Economic implications and investments for the global shipping industry

Dimitrios,Parris.

Postgraduate student of Human Resource Management,
Communication and Leadership.
Department of Management Science and Technology
University of Western Macedonia,
Kozani, Greece.

Dr. Konstantinos Spinthiropoulos

Assistant professor, Department of Management Science and Technology,
University of Western Macedonia,
Kozani, Greece.

Abstract: The article is a bibliographic review of the role of green shipping in tackling air pollution, mainly in the greenhouse effect, with the use of new fuels, free of carbon impurities. Studies on the production and use of hydrogen, ammonia and natural gas as propulsion fuels for ships are reviewed, as well as the advantages and disadvantages of these fuels. Finally, an overview of the economic issues that arise in the shipping industry, from the need to switch to ecological fuels and solutions are proposed to address it as well as possible investments for the utilization of the above fuels.

Keywords: Green shipping, Eco-fuel, Ammonia, Hydrogen, LNG, Environmental protection, Green House Gas, Shipping investments.

I. Introduction

1.1 Introduction of fuel.

Undoubtedly, one of the key sectors to meet the operational needs of industry, production and transportation, is energy. Energy is also the driving force in the shipping industry. All ships that operate at sea for the transport of goods and not only, consume huge amounts of energy every day in order to operate their engines. To produce this required energy, the ships mainly use internal combustion engines (ICEs), consuming liquid conventional fuel, that is a mixture of hydrogen (H₂) and carbon (C₁₂) atoms. These fuels are divided into Heavy Sulfur Fuel Oil (HSFO) and Low Sulfur Fuel Oil (LSFO)[1], depending on their sulfur content. The main reason for using these fuels is the relatively low cost of production, sale and storage, in relation to their high energy efficiency. The opposite of the positive effects of using Marine Gasoil by the shipping industry is the emission of carbon dioxide (CO₂), sulfur oxides (SO_x) and nitrogen oxides (NO_x) into the atmosphere. The above-mentioned emissions of gaseous gases are usually responsible for the creation and intensification of the greenhouse effect (GHG) and the global warming, due to the destruction of ozone (O₃) layers in the atmosphere. The first part of this article takes a quick look at the properties, advantages and disadvantages of conventional fuels used by marine engines. There is also little reference to the history that led to the adoption of measures to reduce greenhouse gas emissions that are responsible for the greenhouse effect, and finally, questions are raised about shipping, in relation to its transition to the era of ecological fuels. The second part refers to hydrogen, ammonia and natural gas but also to the properties, advantages and disadvantages of using these fuels. The third part includes economic issues that the global shipping industry has to face, due to the use of carbonated gases but also

possible investments for the adoption and exploitation of the above situation, by outlining some models that can be used for investment decisions. The article concludes with general conclusions regarding the use of the three aforementioned fuels but also the economic implications and opportunities created in shipping.

1.2. Historical background of the reduction measure.

The European Union has set a goal of phasing out fuels by 2050, a proposal originally adopted by the United States and the United Kingdom. The issue then became a goal of the International Maritime Organization (IMO) which, has now set as a goal the complete decarbonization of fuels by 2050, starting in 2008.

1.3. Shipping issues

But how can the reduction of the use of conventional fuels and finally the elimination of fuels that contain chemical elements, that during their combustion, pollute the atmosphere with the above consequences, be achieved? What investments and financial measures should be taken by the shipping companies in order to obtain the appropriate infrastructure for the use of ecological fuels while at the same time quickly amortizing the costs? What will happen to existing marine engines, given that the life of a ship ranges from 20 to 30 years, which means that a ship that is being built today and costs some billions of dollars, in 5 or maybe ten years will still be considered new, but will not have engines suitable for burning eco-fuels, that will make it unsuitable for operating in controlled areas of green fuels?

The shipping industry focuses on the use of green fuels. Hydrogen (H₂), ammonia (NH₃) and natural gas (L.N.G.) are energy sources that meet the energy needs of zero-emission fuels that are hazardous to the atmosphere.

II. Clean fuels

2.1. Hydrogen

Hydrogen in its simplest form (H₂), is the most "pure" element, that during combustion, guarantees zero emissions of toxic gases. Although there are opinions about the production of nitrogen oxides during combustion, due to the nitrogen that is present in the atmosphere [1]. Adapting marine engines in using hydrogen, could lead to better energy efficiencies, compared to the use of hydrocarbons, due to its high gravitational density and high flammability. However, given the aforementioned flammability of about 4% to 77%, [2] hydrogen can be an explosive fuel during transport, storage and use by ships.

Hydrogen, under normal conditions, is in the atmosphere in gaseous form, up to the critical temperature of 33° K (-240°C) [3]. Its gravitational energy density is relatively high, about 0.033 MWh / kg, but its volumetric energy density is much lower, about 0.003 MWh / m³ at 1 bar [4]. This in turn means that, there is a need for huge storage spaces on the ship for its storage.

One way to deal with the storage problem is to store hydrogen at a high pressure of 700 Bar [5]. This could lead to a solution to the storage problem and at the same time increase the energy efficiency of hydrogen from 1.4 to 2.1 MWh / m³ [6][7]. At the same time, however, this solution requires the construction of high-pressure storage facilities, that creates increased construction's costs for shipping companies [1]. But such a cost is likely to be an investment for shipping, that will bring rapid depreciation, higher profits due to lower hydrogen fuel prices and improved climate impact from non-hydrocarbon use.

Another method of solving the problem is to store hydrogen in liquid form. Maintaining the element in this form requires constant temperatures from 13.8 to 33.2 degrees Kelvin [8]. The liquid form provides a much higher energy efficiency of hydrogen, reaching 2.2 to 2.8 MWh / m³ [8]. However, much higher and continuous energy costs are required to maintain these temperatures in order to be stored by the cryogenic method, that makes the use of this method rather unprofitable [1].

One possible method that could potentially have an effect on the use of hydrogen in shipping, would be to take seawater and convert it to hydrogen by electrolysis. The hydrogen's storage in a tank, will ensure the energy's supply to the ship for a certain period of time, and then will supply the ship's engines through a small capacity tank, in which the consumed hydrogen will be constantly replenished through electrolysis. Ship's engines must be adapted to the use of hydrogen. However, it must first be considered whether the hourly rate of hydrogen production by this method could meet the hourly consumption needs of the engine.

It should be noted here that the annual needs for hydrogen production is about 70 million tons, due to its multiple uses and mainly fuel refining and ammonia production.

2.2. Ammonia

Ammonia is a chemical compound of Nitrogen and Hydrogen. The chemical formula for ammonia is NH_3 . Ammonia is a carrier of high concentrations of Hydrogen. For this reason, as well as the fact that the density of hydrogen it offers, is higher than the density offered by liquid hydrogen per unit volume, it may well be used as an alternative fuel [9][10]. Also, unlike hydrogen which is not in free form and must be prepared by electrolysis, there is a large stock of ammonia, as it is produced by industry in large quantities due to its many uses [10]. It can be produced in many ways through other fuels of all kinds, as well as with electricity or nuclear energy, but also through renewable energy sources, such as solar, wind, geothermal, etc. [10][11]

In addition, due to the characteristic properties such as the strong odor, but also the high flash point, ammonia becomes a relatively safe fuel. Finally, as its volumetric energy density is much higher than that of liquid hydrogen, its storage requires much less space, ultimately making its storage and transport easier than the hydrogen's storage. [9][10]

But in addition to the advantages of ammonia, there are disadvantages to using it as a fuel. Research and experimental studies are underway to address the problems posed by ammonia combustion.

Ammonia has a low combustion rate (SL) when used in internal combustion engines, while at the same time due to this low rate, a large percentage of nitrogen oxides (NO_x) [10][12] are produced. These elements are largely responsible for climate change, the greenhouse effect but also for the presence of smog and acid rain.

Efforts are being made to face the problem, mainly by amplifying the combustion flame with additional fuel. In this way, an attempt is made to increase the rate of ammonia combustion with the consequence of reducing nitrogen oxide emissions into the atmosphere. Blends of NH_3 and H_2 can reduce nitrogen oxide emissions to concentrations of less than 5 ppm when combusted at pressures greater than 10 Atm. [10][13]

In any case, the search for new blends that can increase the rate of ammonia combustion while reducing nitrogen dioxide emissions, continues without immediate satisfactory results.

2.3. Natural Gas

According to the article by Mazyan et.al. (2016), published entitled "Market and technology review of natural gas processing: A review". Published in the "Journal of Natural Gas Science and Engineering", [14] some of the elements of natural gas but also the procedures in the cases to reach the final disposal for sale, are the following:

Liquefied natural gas is a hydrocarbon, consisting of compounds such as methane, ethane, propane, butane and is followed by additional compounds, consisting of 5 carbon atoms and above (eg pentane, hexane, octane and so on). In addition, it contains additional hydro-chemical elements, such as liquid mercury, nitrogen gas, hydrogen sulfide and carbon dioxide, as well as various hazardous solid particles. It is by far the most suitable fuel solution after oil, as it has a high energy efficiency during combustion, while at the same time, the emissions of carbon dioxide (CO_2), a gas that is largely responsible for the greenhouse effect and the global warming, are much reduced in relation to the emissions caused by oil combustion.

The conversion of natural gas into its final form, as a fuel, a long process is required, including extraction, refining, liquification and regasification.

The extraction starts from the underground with technique such as filling the underground tanks with water in order to make a way to the surface, pouring chemicals or other gaseous mixtures. After the gas is collected in its original form, it is transported to the refineries where the fuel separates from the other harmful elements and particles, that, as mentioned above, can be liquids such as mercury, gases such as hydrogen sulfide or solid particles. Then it transports into tanks, to its final disposal on the market.

To complete its transportation, the natural gas is liquefied by cooling to -160°C . In this way, its volume is greatly reduced. As a result, it can be transported and stored by means such as ships and trucks, and even by pipeline.

3.1 Implications

Turning to zero-carbon fuels requires a wealth of shipping infrastructure. According to Baldi et al., (2014), propulsion engines are huge energy storage depots that reach 68% of the ship's annual energy demand (17) (18) (18)

But what will happen in the future? Some shipping companies of Greek interests have already placed an order for the supply of their ships under construction, with new type engines, capable of using new type of gaseous fuels. However, studies for the construction and production of engines of this type are still at a primary stage, thus making it virtually impossible for the company to calculate the cost of construction and the absolute compatibility with the new fuels in combination with their efficiency and consumption. In addition, it is still difficult to predetermine further technical characteristics for the above reasons as well as for the fact, that we do not yet fully know the behavior of these fuels during their combustion in the engine. And one more question that arises, is the most fuel will eventually be selected as the most suitable for the propulsion of ships. And more appropriate, means the combination of production, distribution and performance costs. The choice of hybrid engine construction is an issue that should concern marine engine manufacturers as well as shipping companies, as a study should be made on the possibility of using two or more fuels from the same engine and what will the fuel be? And while a ship has an average life expectancy of 25 years, maybe a little more, what will happen to the engines that are currently being built before the studies are completed and which a decade from now will still be considered new. And if we assume that a possible end in terms of the most suitable fuel as well as the technical characteristics of the engines under construction seems to be fading, what will happen to the newer ships or the slightly older ones, which already have Diesel internal combustion engines? Will they already be considered old technology in a few years? Will they be out of competition making it impossible for these ships to operate, initially in reduced or zero emission control areas? Is their conversion beneficial for the use of new gaseous fuels or is it unprofitable for the shipping industry? These are questions that should be answered relatively immediately, by the global marine engine industry.

An equally important issue for the shipping industry about the transition to the green age, is fuel's storage and disposal infrastructure, given that gaseous fuels requires either very high pressure reservoirs or the constant consumption of vast amounts of energy, for cooling and keeping gases in liquid form, in order to take up less space and have a higher energy efficiency than in gaseous form. Is it possible to build such tanks? And if so, is there any space required on board?

A third issue that arises, is the safety of ships, as gases such as hydrogen if selected, are explosive and pose immediate risks to the safety of work on ships.

Finally, one of the most important issues that arise is the vessel's refueling. Is it possible to have the constantly needed quantities to meet global energy needs? Will any ship be able to be served in any port it arrives? Will these types of fuel be available in every area where ships arrive? How will the fuel be sold in such markets, especially in third countries which have increased maritime traffic but do not have the appropriate transport and storage infrastructure? What will happen to free charter ships, not having specific destination port, assuming that the proper supply infrastructure, will be initially created only in the largest ports in the world?

3.2 Marine Investments

Realizing the importance and immediacy of developments, the shipping community must act in a timely manner to address the problems that appears to arise in the near future. Investment studies should be prepared by the financial sector of the companies in order to benefit from the transition to the green season.

The commission has already put forward a proposal for the imposition of a carbon tax on fuels, while at the same time the exemption or reduction of the tonnage tax for ships that will turn to green shipping has been put on the table, thus creating so many disincentives for the use of hydrocarbons in the coming years, as well as incentives to shift shipping to eco-fuels, in order to comply with the requirements of the International Maritime Organization, to reduce emissions that leads to the maintenance and increase of the greenhouse effect.

Grants to research organizations and manufacturers of marine engines, could be considered a form of investment, as it will strengthen research to find solutions to the issue of engine construction and the selection and manufacture of the most appropriate fuel. This will be made available directly to the global shipping community, enabling more confident

decisions, both in the type of machines that will be requested from the construction companies, and in making additional financial and business decisions, such as the type and duration of charters and areas in which they will choose to be active. All of the above should be studied, both in terms of laboratory research, on the know-how of fuels and engines, and in terms of economic and technical research through mathematical models. These models with the introduction of parameters such as the cost of production, transport and sale of fuel, the cost of construction and supply of new type naval engines, the hourly consumption of engines and the total cost of each trip, will export data. Using them, each company will predict the performance of its business in time and will formulate its business and financial strategy.

At the same time, in this way and given that the know-how and the disposal of fuel will be available to the wider society, further reducing dangerous gas emissions, ensuring the longevity of the planet, health and improving the economy, every shipping company that will participate in research projects, and will promote the image of its Corporate Social Responsibility (C.S.R.).

Another investment project that might be legitimate to run, is the study of the shipbuilding sector for the construction of large-capacity ships, but with reduced water resistance. This will reduce the need for multiple trips to transport cargo, since more goods will be transported by fewer ships, while at the same time, easier movement without many resistances, will mean reduced fuel consumption and thus increase profit from reducing purchase costs, while reducing emissions. But one issue that should be considered by the global shipping industry in such a case is the existing ship docking infrastructure, whether they will be able to accommodate larger capacity ships and how much larger ones.

The orientation of the shipping companies, initially in the conclusion of cargo transportation contracts on itineraries, in order to avoid individual journeys, focusing on long-term charters, of course ensuring income but also the coverage of their energy needs, will be another parameter, that if not increase the profit, will maintain it stable and will lead in the smooth transition of shipping to the new situation.

Finally, assuming that an investment program to verticalize companies and merge them with oil companies and port facilities, or even to acquire them, is probably impossible, it may be appropriate to consider their horizontal development. By this way, joining strategic plan with fuel companies, construction of engines as well as port facility management bodies, the total cost of a trip may be reduced while also the aforementioned businesses or organizations will be developed.

IV. Conclusion

In summary, the purpose of this paper is to summarize through bibliographic reviews the importance of issues that concern and will continue to concern the global maritime community, in terms of meeting its energy needs and in compliance with the standards of the International Maritime creating green shipping and protecting the atmosphere. Through references to the basic characteristics of the fuels, an attempt was made to provide comparative measures that facilitate the final selection of ecological fuel gases. Potential economic impacts on shipping were highlighted, as well as the importance of an immediate response, through investment proposals to avoid the risk of an economic collapse of the shipping industry. Due to the large number of data and observations, it is not possible to include an extensive analysis of all the characteristics and technical specifications of mining - fuel generation in this paper. In addition to the bibliographic references, some of the author's ideas - suggestions are included, which can be the trigger for further studies, both technical and investment.

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